

THE IMPORTANCE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGY IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Annotation: *This article describes the great importance given to foreign languages in our country and the innovative technologies needed to study them, to improve skills in working with them, the methodology of teaching foreign languages, which is becoming a requirement of the time.*

Keywords: *Foreign languages, information and communication technologies, listening comprehension, efficiency, methodical games.*

After the independence of our country, the interest in teaching foreign languages has grown and many opportunities have been created for young people. As the first President Islam Karimov said, "At present, great importance is attached to the teaching of foreign languages in our country. This, of course, is not in vain. There is no need to underestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our countries, which today are striving to take their rightful place in the world community, for our people, who are building their great future in cooperation with our foreign partners. "As a logical continuation of these ideas, the Presidential Decree of December 10, 2012 "On Measures to Further Improve the System of Teaching Foreign Languages" expanded the opportunities for learning foreign languages. New methods and requirements for teaching foreign languages in the country have been developed in accordance with the recommendations of the Pan-European Framework for Assessment of Knowledge and Skills of Foreign Language Teachers (CEFR). According to him, textbooks have been created for students of secondary schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms are equipped with stands and new information and communication technologies. The demand for learning a foreign language is growing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, reading, listening comprehension, and speaking), each of which provides specific concepts and skills. Educational technology is the effective use of modern information technology in the educational process. It also aims to improve the quality and effectiveness of education through the introduction of modern innovative technologies in the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages to using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is invaluable. The use of technology is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, reading, listening and speaking). For example, to listen and understand, of course, it is impossible to do this process without a computer, player, CDs. Listening is one of the most important parts of language learning. This requires the student to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, grammatical rules, vocabulary, and meanings at the same time. An important

factor in the use of modern technologies in education is the ability of students to know and use information and communication technologies. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technology is one of the most effective ways. In this process, including: - when using computers, the student can watch and hear videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons in a foreign language; - It is possible to listen and watch radio broadcasts in foreign languages and TV programs; - use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are more traditional methods; - CD players are available. The use of these tools will make the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students. Today, interactive games are becoming a tradition in schools. It is well known that a variety of games help students demonstrate their abilities, focus, increase their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. The basis of the use of game technology is the activity that activates and accelerates the student. According to psychologists, the psychological mechanisms of playful activity are based on the fundamental needs of the individual to express themselves, to find a stable place in life, to self-manage, to realize their potential. At the heart of any game should be the generally accepted principles and tactics of education. Learning games should be based on the subjects. During the games, the student is more interested in this activity than in a normal lesson and works more comfortably. It should be noted that the game is, first of all, a way of teaching. Students are interested in playful lessons, they strive to win, and the teacher uses them to educate the student. The student is interested in believing that he or she can play, speak, listen, understand, and write in English. We know that in the current educational process, the student must be a subject. Focusing on more interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English lessons is to teach students to think independently. Today, English teachers use the following innovative methods, based on the experience of educators in the United States and the United States: - "Creative Problem Solving" To use this method, the beginning of the story is read and how it ends. students are referred to the judgment of the students; - Merry Riddles is an important part of teaching English to students, as they learn words they are unfamiliar with and find the answer to a riddle; - Quick answers help to increase the effectiveness of the lesson; - "Warm-up exercises" use a variety of games in the classroom to engage students in the lesson; - Pantomime can be used in a class where very difficult topics need to be explained or when students are tired of writing exercises; - A chain story method helps to develop students' oral skills; - Acting characters This method can be used in all types of lessons. Professionals such as Interpreter, Translator, Writer, and Poet can participate in the class and talk to students; - Poets and writers such as W. Shakespeare, A. Navoi, R. Burns can be "invited" to the "Meeting of Scholars". At such times, the use of the wise sayings they utter in the classroom will help young people to become perfect human beings; - The "When pictures speak" method is more convenient and helps to teach English, to develop students' oral speech, it is necessary to use thematic pictures; - Quiz cards are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to attend classes at the same time, which saves time. As we have seen, each innovative technology has its own set of advantages. All of these methods involve collaboration between teacher and student, active participation of the student in the educational process. In short, the use of innovative methods in English lessons develops students' logical thinking skills, fluency, and the ability to respond

quickly and accurately. Such methods stimulate the student's desire for knowledge. The student strives to prepare well for the lessons. This makes students active participants in the learning process. As the education system sets itself the task of nurturing a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future we will contribute to the further development of effective ways for future teachers to effectively use innovative technologies.

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